

GENDER ROLE: HUMAN BEHAVIOR

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Abstract. *This article highlights the history of the emergence of the term “gender role”, ideas about behavior based on the concepts of masculinity and femininity and their meaning in society, gender role categories and characteristics.*

Keywords: *gender, society, behavior, gender role, marriage, evolution, culture.*

Introduction. In accordance with the decision of the Senate of the Supreme Assembly of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. SQ -297- IV dated May 28, 2021 on the approval of the Strategy for achieving gender equality in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, the issue of ensuring gender equality locally was raised to the level of state policy in the upper house of parliament, the Committee on women's affairs and gender equality issues, Republican Commission on Gender Equality and Family Issues, Increasing the role of women in society, Consultations on issues. On issues of ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men - councils, the Republican Women's Public Council was created [1].

The activities of the media are also important for the promotion and achievement of gender equality. There has been an increase in the number of radio and television programs that reflect the image of modern socially and politically active women and highlight the opportunities created for women and men.

The main goal of the gender strategy is to ensure real equality of women and men, regardless of race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, faith, personal and social status. Gender equality is one of the most pressing problems in the field of psychology [2].

Feminism played a decisive role in the emergence of gender theory, which today has become an alternative theory of sociocultural development. Gender equality and sexual equality, more precisely equality between men and women, is a concept and other legal relations that presuppose the achievement of equal rights between men and women in the family and society. A culturally and socially defined set of expected behaviors, attitudes, and characteristics based on gender roles and concepts of masculinity and femininity. Gender role should not be confused with gender identity, which refers to a person's internal sense of masculinity and femininity on a spectrum in between, non-binary gender, or no gender at all.

Analysis of literature on the topic . The term “gender role” was first used in print in 1955 by New Zealand-born American sexologist John Money. Poole defined it as “anything a person says or does to reveal their status as a boy, man, or girl.” or a woman." Although the term was not defined until 1955, throughout history most societies have had gender roles for men and women. For example, beginning in the early 19th century, many European societies defined men and women as having different roles in society. to the Victorian gender ideology of distinct areas, which emphasized the roles for which they were created [3] .

Gender roles fall into several categories. Some gender stereotypes describe how adult men and women function in families. In 20th-century Western culture, in a two-parent family with children, the husband was typically the breadwinner and the wife was the homemaker. However, these dynamics changed dramatically in the second half of the twentieth century and beyond.

Traditionally male occupations include engineering and medicine, as well as jobs requiring a high level of technical skill or physical strength. Traditionally women's occupations include teaching and secretarial work, as well as care work such as babysitting and childcare. Today, such stereotypes are being seriously challenged, with women holding nearly a third of STEM (science, technology, engineering and mathematics) jobs. In addition, a quarter of teaching positions are held by men. Gender roles include expectations related to appearance: American men typically wear shorter haircuts and pants, and women often wear longer hairstyles and dresses or skirts in certain social situations.

Research methodology. Methods of gender research. Methods from the humanities and natural sciences are actively involved in the subject area of genderology, new methods are being developed and traditional scientific methodology is being revised. Research methods of gender studies can be borrowed from both natural scientific disciplines and the humanities and social sciences. Consequently, it is equally permissible to talk about the applicability of psychodiagnostic methods, quantitative and qualitative methods of sociology, the method of historicism, interpretive strategies of the humanities and some social sciences, and quantitative methods of biological sciences. Therefore, we can conclude that “gender studies is currently not a discipline, but rather an interdisciplinary field of research” [4]. In gender studies in social work, sociological methods are most often used P.V. Romanov, E.R. Yarskaya-Smirnova Research in social work: assessment, analysis, examination. There are quantitative and qualitative research methodologies.

In quantitative - mass social research, a specific person is not considered as a unique individual, but only as a representative of a certain gender, age, occupation, type of behavior, that is, as a representative of a certain group.

- As a result of quantitative research, an array of data is accumulated, and since the relationships in quantitative research are statistical in nature, the number of respondents is of great importance here.

Conclusions and offers. It should be noted that most research on gender roles is based on traditional heterosexual Western gender roles. Some theorists also describe two additional types of gender roles: egalitarian and transitional. Egalitarian gender roles mean that each gender has equal responsibility for working outside the home, running the household, and raising children. Within transitional gender roles, each gender may devote time to work, home, and family, but men are expected to devote more energy to work and women to housekeeping and child-rearing.

Gender schema theory provides a useful framework for understanding how knowledge structures about gender are formed, but it is not without its critics. One of the theory's weaknesses is that it cannot explain how biology or social interactions influence gender development. Moreover, the content of the gender schema remains unclear. Although theory is intended to explain the process rather than the content of these patterns, they are difficult to measure without understanding their content. Finally, gender-related cognitive schemas have been shown to predict thinking, attention, and memory, but they are less predictive of behavior. Therefore, a person's gender schema may not match the behavior that he exhibits.

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